

Master Thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Using Perceptual Timbre Descriptors to Browse Large Audio Collections

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August 2020

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Acknowledgement

I would like to thank Frederic Font for his constant support and encouragement with this thesis, Xavier Favory for valuable insight at specific points during the project, and Perfecto Herrera for a few talks that I'm sure have influenced my approach and interests. And of course I'd like to thank my partner, who has endured the whole process and supported me when needed, and my parents for having made all this time of learning at sunny Barcelona possible.

Abstract

We investigate the use of perceptually-modelled descriptors of timbre for browsing large collections of user-contributed sound. Such descriptors are already available in the sound-sharing site Freesound through their public API but have been largely unexplored for regular use. A large-scale analysis of the statistical behaviour of these descriptors is presented. We believe such analysis has not been performed before in MIR outside of the context of model-driven feature extraction. Such analysis is then used to inform the design of a search results-filtering interface, based on range sliders, that makes use of these timbral descriptors. We end the study with an evaluation of such interface on actual Freesound users through the use of online surveying. We believe our proposed browsing interface using perceptually-modelled descriptors can provide novel and useful ways of navigating large sound collections.

Keywords: audio browsing; timbre; high-level acoustic descriptors

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Current digital technologies, such as smartphones, laptop computers and ubiquitous networking, enable easy generation and near-immediate sharing of data. Audio recordings are part of this growing corpus of information. Information retrieval research aims at making sense of growing databases and finding ways of better navigating them. In their study of automatic description of “whoosh” sounds, Cherny et al. [1] state the need for audio retrieval and browsing systems in professional audiovisual media environments where auditioning long lists of samples is not an efficient solution, for example by further filtering of conventional textual keyword-based search results.

While tags are an important feature in search results filtering, tags in Freesound ¹ are mostly used to describe the objects that produce the sound, and the attributes of such objects[2]. This matches Gaver’s observation that our perception of sound is ecological[3]: it depends on the materials of the objects making the sound, and the kind of interaction that is causing the vibration of these materials (as well as the environment in which all this happens). However, search by acoustic attributes is less common. For example, aside from filtering search results by tag, file type, bit-

¹<https://freesound.org/>

depth, or pack (i.e. sounds grouped together by a contributing user), users may want to filter search results by perceptual sound qualities such as brightness, coarseness, or tonal-definition. This behaviour could be implemented as part of Freesound's faceted search system. Faceted search has been found to be preferred by users for browsing, as stated by Baeza-Yates & Nibeiro-Neto [4]:

"Usability studies find that users like, and are successful, using faceted navigation, if the interface is designed properly, and that faceted interfaces are overwhelmingly preferred for collection search and browsing as an alternative to the standard keyword-and-results listing interface."

These filters should be relevant to the category of sound being queried. According to research by Martínez et al. [2], and Font and Serra [5], *field-recording* constitutes the top tag used on the site, followed by *drum* and other instrumental samples, as well as *noise* and other electronic noises. From these three broad categories, a search by timbral attributes may be most appropriate for noises and electronic sounds whose source is difficult to identify, either in absolute terms or by comparison to other sounds. However, these filters could prove useful in enriching the browsing experience for instrumental sounds and field-recordings too.

Roma et al. [6], working on sound-event modelling for automatic classification, analyse the presence of Gaver's environmental sound taxonomy [3] in Freesound's *folksonomy*. They find that the taxonomy is much less represented in Freesound's *folksonomy* than in two other structured sound-effect databases, and thus argue that "a content-based approach should facilitate the retrieval of sounds in unstructured databases" [6]. Similarly, we argue that a system for search results filtering leveraging perceptual descriptors may add further functionality to users' search experience in Freesound.

Specifically, using perceptual descriptors can bring a greater degree of serendipity and surprise. Whilst professional musicians may not be a common profile within the Freesound user-base, creative work can indeed be assumed to be a typical use case for Freesound content. In the particular context of creative uses of retrieval

systems, Andersen and Knees provide qualitative insight into users' needs from a series of 33 interviews with professional electronic music producers [7]. Amongst other concerns, authors found that:

- Interviewees considered surprise and serendipity to be important aspects in their work.
- Interviewees expressed a need for non-textual semantic representation of sounds in retrieval tools.

Siedenburg et al. [8] reviewed the state of disparity between timbral descriptor usage in MIR versus music psychology research, and pointed out how necessary perceptually informed descriptions of sound become when “the modelled phenomena are of inherently psychological nature” [8]. Luckily, Freesound already provides perceptual descriptors through its API calculated for sounds of 30 seconds or shorter. However, this data is not currently being leveraged for search and browsing purposes, and the validity of these descriptors has not yet been assessed in a sound search task context. These descriptors are a product of research by Pearce et al. [9] as part of the AudioCommons Initiative. The Audio Commons Initiative aimed to promote “the use of open audio content” and to develop “technologies with which to support an envisioned ecosystem of content repositories, production tools and users (the AudioCommons Ecosystem)”². Some of the research involved focused on timbre, since much of the available Creative Commons content consists of sound effects and field recordings. As a result, they published a set of perceptual audio descriptors, which are now part of Freesound’s standard server-side audio analysis. They developed models for the most-searched timbral attributes on Freesound: *brightness*, *hardness*, *boominess*, *roughness*, *sharpness*, *warmth*, and *depth*.

This thesis proposes the use of high-level perceptually-modelled timbral descriptors to filter out search results and, in doing so, provide a non-textual semantic alternative to text-based queries and filtering by tags or file metadata. This perceptual navigation may facilitate a quicker discovery of sounds that would be cumbersome

²<https://www.audiocommons.org/about/>

to access (e.g. by iterative text queries, metadata filtering, changing the sorting mechanism, or having to navigate to other result pages), thus addressing issues of surprise and serendipity important for creative work.

1.2 Objectives

The aim of this thesis is to analyse the behaviour of perceptual audio descriptors in large unstructured databases (such as Freesound), and the possibilities they may offer for search and browsing. We will study the behaviour of these descriptors first in a mid-scale dataset of environmental sounds. Then we will apply this analysis to results from some of the most popular Freesound queries. This will inform the design of a website prototype for search results filtering which, at the last stage of this thesis is evaluated through an online experiment with Freesound users.

Several outcomes are expected as a result of this research:

- An analysis of the distribution, correlation, and information content of perceptual audio descriptor values.
- An investigation of how this analysis changes when the search results considered are scaled up or down.
- A prototype of an interface that makes use these descriptors to filter search results and integrates well with the existing faceted search system in Freesound, contributing to users' experience.
- An evaluation of how useful our proposed filtering system is for users in exploratory search.

1.3 Structure of the Report

In the next chapter, we will give an overview of existing research in the different areas of work needed throughout this thesis: perceptual high-level audio descriptors, audio browsing interfaces, and audio feature analysis.

Chapter 3 specifies our methods for the descriptor analysis, prototype design process, and evaluation. In chapter 4 we show the results of our descriptor analysis and user evaluation. Lastly, chapter 5 discusses possible further improvements to the prototype according to our results, and how this could be integrated in production with the Freesound site.

Chapter 2

Related Work

2.1 Available Perceptual Descriptors

Aforementioned research in the AudioCommons project by Pearce et al. [9] provides a set of open-source descriptors which capture intuitive aspects of sound timbre, unlike some lower-level audio descriptors. Additionally, these are already part of the analysis performed by Freesound on all sounds of up to 30 seconds. These descriptors are frame-wise or onset-wise computations which are then averaged, most often using the \log_{10} of an arithmetic mean over time. They are spectral only, and the averaging over time (into what is sometimes known as summary descriptors) means temporal detail is lost. Whilst this should not be problematic for high and low extremes, it may be misleading for mid-valued sounds, where descriptor values may be distributed differently over time. This is supported by Peeters et al. [10] who state that mean and standard deviation as summarization statistics for time-varying descriptors are dramatically influenced by outliers (such as silence segments), and propose instead the median and interquartile range as more robust measures.

Thomas Grill's [11] proposed descriptors cover a mix of spectral: high-low, tonal-noisy; and temporal modelling: smooth-coarse, ordered-chaotic, and homogeneous-heterogeneous. These model time by means of various differentiations and integrations along the time axis, variants of autocorrelation, and Fourier transforms of

sonograms, effectively measuring fluctuation patterns [12] along frequency bands in time. This also is reminiscent of McDermott & Simoncelli’s inclusion of modulation bands in their auditory model. They argue in [13] that statistical moments of these modulation bands may allow the "distinction between rapidly modulated sounds (e.g., insect vocalizations) and slowly modulated sounds (e.g., ocean waves)." Such *textural descriptors* may prove useful for browsing some categories of sounds, especially since they model temporal aspects that are more lacking in Pearce’s et al. [9] timbral models. However, part of the motivation for this thesis lies in the reuse of existing resources: i.e. AudioCommons timbral descriptors data already present in Freesound’s API analysis resources.

Name	Description ¹
<i>brightness</i>	Brightness of the analyzed audio in a scale from [0-100]. A bright sound is one that is clear/vibrant and/or contains significant high-pitched elements.
<i>depth</i>	Depth of the analyzed audio in a scale from [0-100]. A deep sound is one that conveys the sense of having been made far down below the surface of its source.
<i>hardness</i>	Hardness of the analyzed audio in a scale from [0-100]. A hard sound is one that conveys the sense of having been made (i) by something solid, firm or rigid; or (ii) with a great deal of force.
<i>roughness</i>	Roughness of the analyzed audio in a scale from [0-100]. A rough sound is one that has an uneven or irregular sonic texture.
<i>boominess</i>	Boominess of the analyzed sound in a scale from [0-100]. A boomy sound is one that conveys a sense of loudness, depth and resonance.
<i>warmth</i>	Warmth of the analyzed sound in a scale from [0-100]. A warm sound is one that promotes a sensation analogous to that caused by a physical increase in temperature.
<i>sharpness</i>	Sharpness of the analyzed sound in a scale from [0-100]. A sharp sound is one that suggests it might cut if it were to take on physical form.

Table 1: Descriptors Used

Roma et al. [6] use a combination of low-level features from the MPEG7 specifications, and then compute a set of statistics from the time series of these per-frame features to capture temporal aspects of sounds. This is in line with McDermott & Simoncelli’s [13] proposed auditory model, based on between-cochlear-band marginal moments (mean, variance, skew, kurtosis) and correlations, as well as modulation band marginal moments, and between-cochlear-band and within-cochlear-band modulation band correlations.

Most recent research using high-level perceptual audio descriptors at the user level

¹Description retrieved from https://freesound.org/docs/api/resources_apiv2.html#text-search

(i.e. not simply as features to solve another problem) seems centered on synthesis. Some examples are Soraghan's et al. [14] work on visualization of perceptual acoustic attributes according to acoustic features extracted from synthesised sound, Ramires' et al. [15] work on synthesised drum sounds by mapping timbral descriptors to audio waveforms of the audio they were extracted from, or Esling's et al. research [16], also on neural synthesis based on perceptual metrics of timbre. However, our focus is on audio browsing, so next section will give an overview of research in said field.

2.2 Browsing Interfaces and Search Results Filtering

Aside from conventional ranked lists of results according to a given text-based query, the majority of approaches to audio file browsing make use of 2D graphics in some way. In 2003, Tzanetakis [17] presented some of the earliest audio browser design that allowed users to search audio tracks (loops or songs) by genre, tempo and other continuous attributes such as "spectral brightness" and "beat strength" through User Interface (UI) elements he called *SoundSliders* and *SoundLists*. However, according to the published paper, only genre list and tempo slider were ever included in the user study. In the study, 6 users had to find a match for a given audio file within a 200 file collection using their proposed UI or a traditional directory-tree one; this UI choice was randomized across trials, and each user did 5 trials. He found tempo information to have statistically significant effects on users' speed in finding a match, but UI choice seemed to have no advantages.

Pampalk et al. [18] built a browsing system comprised of a hierarchy tree and a graphic display, the former produced using 1-dimensional Self-Organizing Maps (SOM), and the latter produced using 2-dimensional SOMs from sonogram similarity distance measures. See figure 1 below. Through an informal demo with 5 prospective users, they found that fewer hierarchical levels were desired: this could mean simpler, less busy interfaces are preferred, although the study was inconclusive. Also, users' wanted to be able to browse samples according to words such as dark, thick, or

crispy.

Figure 1: Drum Sample Explorer based on 1-dimensional and 2-dimensional SOMs proposed by Pampalk et al. [18].

Streich and Ong [19] proposed another 2D graphical user interface for browsing collections of musical loops. Sounds from the collection are represented as circles on a 2D plane. The audio descriptors *spectral centroid*, *bass ratio*, *energy* and *BPM* are mapped to x-axis, y-axis, color and size of the circles. The user can move the circles around if they overlap, click on them to preview the sounds, adjust master tempo and volume settings, filter by non-numeric metadata (e.g. instrument category), and scale the four audio descriptors logarithmically or quadratically to change the distribution of results on the 2D plane. Although authors do not provide an objective user evaluation with their technical report, they observe that, while overall similarity may be more useful in contexts such as searching song collections, in the context of browsing loops users may want access to specific properties of the displayed sounds:

"It might for example be interesting to find an item with a very noisy

sound characteristic for mixing it with a clean, tonal loop. Or one might look for a loop with the energy concentrated in the bass region in order to add some 'punch' to a mix." [19]

This matches users' impressions of Pampalk's system:

"[...] it would be very useful to classify samples according to words such as dark, thick, crispy, etc. even if the meaning of these words needs to be more or less arbitrarily predefined." [18]

We consider this aspect (i.e. the usefulness of such high-level perceptual construct for audio browsing, or lack thereof) a fundamental question for our research, and will be a central concern in the design of user evaluation of the presented prototype (See section...). Streich and Ong also make an interesting remark regarding usability:

Our system can currently visualize descriptors with up to four dimensions only. However, when playing with the system we found it already hard to keep these four attributes in mind simultaneously.

This means selecting only the most meaningful descriptors for a given query may ease their use for filtering results.

In the late 2000s more 2-dimensional browsing systems were proposed, but no available testing and user feedback accompanied these research efforts. One such example is Coleman's [20] *Mused* system, focused on audio collage composition, which worked by first creating a personal sample library through audio onset-based segmentation of a personal music library. The generated samples were then placed on a 2d display according to their temporal centroid on the X axis and spectral centroid on the Y axis, and also allowed browsing by pitch class profile and loudness, using range sliders for real-valued attributes. However, the program was never evaluated by users.

Schwarz and Schnell [21] developed a system in which sounds are also presented as points in a 2-dimensional space, but their research focus was on efficient and scalable algorithms for similarity-based search in a multi-dimensional descriptor space: 229 low-level descriptors which are also made available for the user to select as X-axis or Y-axis. However, this also lacked user testing.

Heise et al. [22] proposed another 2D sound browsing interface, except that they use MFCC as base representation in the collection, and then position each sound in the display through a Self-Organizing Map (SOM). What was novel about their particular interface was the use of a "virtual torch" to highlight groups of sounds and play them back through a surround system, using spatialisation to allow concurrent browsing. Techniques such as SOMs and PCA (also used by Schwarz and Schnell [21]) allow the mapping of high-dimensional data into a 2-dimensional representation, but as Streich and Ong point out, "the contribution of an individual descriptor can become completely concealed in this type of visualization" [19], which is not an issue with harder to interpret features such as MFCC or zero-crossing rate, for example, but is undesirable when dealing with semantically meaningful descriptors.

Fried et al. [23] have more recently designed a browsing system based on metric learning to sort sounds into a grid. Their system allowed this sorting to be recomputed upon user re-ordering of the sounds to match their perceived similarity. They performed an online quantitative study that gave 100 users 60 seconds to find as many of 10 snare drum sounds (out of 100 in total) similar to a given target sound as possible. They found that their proposed 2D sorting system (plus a colouring scheme) allowed users to perform better in similarity-based search than randomly sorted or non-coloured interfaces. While being a recent (and user-evaluated) example of audio browsing research, it still deals with MFCC as its base audio representation, not perceptual audio attributes, and is centered on similarity search.

Grill and Flexer are, to the best of our knowledge (as of August 2020), alone in the use of perceptual timbral audio descriptors directly, i.e. keeping the descriptors intact on the users' end, for audio browsing [24]. Their proposed interface uses a 2-dimensional representation, much like others discussed above, in their case us-

Auditory construct	Visual parameter
<i>high</i> → <i>low</i>	brightness + color hue (bright yellow → dark red)
<i>ordered</i> → <i>chaotic</i>	regularity of elements (on grid → deviating from grid)
<i>smooth</i> → <i>coarse</i>	jaggedness of element outline (smooth outline → jagged outline)
<i>tonal</i> → <i>noisy</i>	saturation (colorful → gray)
<i>homogeneous</i> → <i>heterogeneous</i>	variability in color parameters, especially hue (no variation → much variation)

Table 2: Grill and Flexer’s mapping of perceptual auditory qualities to visual qualities (source:)

ing t-SNE [25] for dimensionality-reduction. However, their contribution is using perceptual audio descriptors for visualization. Based on prior research, where they elicited common attributes (personal constructs) used by a range of listeners to describe textural sound, and Grill’s work [11] in proposing a signal processing implementation of those constructs, they propose a direct mapping of the constructs to visual parameters following "metaphoric correspondences between the auditory and visual modalities" [24] (see table 2 for a summary of such metaphoric mapping, and figure 2 for their browsing prototype with the proposed visualization). Additionally, they did perform user testing of their devised mapping. They used an online listening test which asked 134 users to match a reference sound to one of three visualizations given. One of the three visualizations corresponded to the reference sound, generated from its textural descriptor values, while the others were generated from random descriptor values or corresponded to another sound from the collection that was not the target sound. They found that their visualization allowed most subjects to successfully associate a sound to its graphic depiction in an intuitive way. However, users never know about the high-level perceptual constructs (*high-low*, *ordered-chaotic*, *smooth-coarse*, *tonal-noisy*, *homogeneous-heterogeneous*) behind the visualisation of the sound collection.

Figure 2: Grill and Flexer’s web-browser prototype using the proposed visualization scheme based on textural descriptors mapped to parameters of the graphical representation. [24]

The timbral descriptors from the AudioCommons initiative are semantically meaningful descriptors, which are meant to be intuitive as they are for an end user, and a central concern for our research is to assess how valuable such perceptually-informed descriptors are for browsing. The research presented in this chapter gives insight into possible approaches to browsing using perceptual audio descriptors. To explore other approaches and, most importantly, to provide direct access (i.e. not mathematically transformed in any way) to the descriptors, we will explore the usage of these descriptors via a slider-based interface coupled with using distribution information. In the following sections, we will also focus on analysing the information characteristics of these descriptors from a statistical standpoint. The value of such analysis should be two-fold: *i*) it will provide insight into how these perceptual fea-

tures are distributed over large collections of audio, which may give the community clues as to how valuable they may be for other tasks such as classification or similarity search, and *ii*) it will also specifically aid us in building a browsing interface that can provide fast user feedback without comprising accuracy.

2.3 Statistical Analysis of Features

Despite the increasing interest in deep-learning-based audio research, where end-to-end systems are common (e.g. [26]), feature engineering has not disappeared from the research landscape. In deep learning research, feature or representation learning [27] (a concept analogous to feature engineering) has taken hold, and it has been applied to audio problems such as audio classification notably since 2009 [28] and more recently using noisy audio [29]. As the name implies, these approaches "learn" the audio features needed for a given task, so analysing the features is unnecessary.

In other non-deep-learning approaches to common audio problems (e.g. using SVMs [30]), where audio feature engineering is necessary, audio features may be analysed. However, this is often with the only purpose of reducing the amount of data necessary to perform the task at hand, i.e. to pick those features that maximize the performance of the model or system that uses them.

The descriptors under consideration are only seven, so dimensionality of the data is not a problem, especially since they each encode a perceptually meaningful aspect of timbre. Still, we may want to select the few descriptors that are most relevant for a particular user query. This is to some degree related to the type of sound being queried, but we can also assume that the amount of information encoded by a given descriptor or its degree of independence from the others may play a role in how expressive it can be for filtering search results. We will come back to this aspect in section 3.2.

Mitrovic et al, working on the problem of feature selection, state that "redundant features describe similar properties of the underlying data, while statistically independent features contain orthogonal information" [31], and study similarities and

redundancies in MPEG-7 audio feature groups. They propose a measure of the "information contained in a feature with respect to its variance" [31] (which they call "expressiveness" of a feature) based on Principal Component Analysis (PCA). Starting from a matrix of feature vectors of sample audio files, this measure, the Weighted Average Loading Indicator or WALDI, is computed from a PCA of the feature data, keeping the principal components with an Eigenvalue greater than or equal to 1, since any less explains less variance than the original audio does. Then they extract the factor loading matrix, of size *principal components x features* (rows, columns). Here, features loading the same principal components are correlated. Then WALDI is calculated according to the following equation:

$$WALDI(f_j) = \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^C \sigma^2(c_i)} \sum_{i=1}^C |L(c_i, td_j)| \sigma^2(c_i) \quad (2.1)$$

Where f_j is the j -th feature from set F of audio features, c_i are the C principal components with Eigenvalue greater than one, $\sigma^2(c_i)$ denotes the variance explained by the i -th principal component, and L is the $(C \times F)$ real-valued matrix of factor loadings. Mitrovic et al. [31] compared their proposed measure to information entropy [32], determined by:

$$H(f) = - \sum_{i=1}^n p(i) \log_2 p(i) \quad (2.2)$$

Where $n = 256$ quantization bins of observed feature values, $p(i)$ is the probability of the i -th bin for a feature f , and thus $H(f)$ is the entropy of a feature in *bits per byte*. In contrast, to analyse the redundancy of MPEG7 audio descriptors, Peeters et al. [10] employed a correlation distance metric based on the Spearman rank correlation of each pair of summarized descriptor values over a database of musical sounds. Since they deal with a total of 32 descriptors, they use hierarchical clustering and multidimensional scaling to produce groups from the resulting 32x32 correlation

distance matrices, where each distance matrix is given by:

$$D = 1 - |\rho_S(ad_{rt}, ad'_{r't'})| \quad (2.3)$$

Where ρ_S stands for the Spearman rank correlation, ad and ad' are two audio descriptor summary values, and r and t refer to different base audio representation and summary statistic, respectively (since those are the elements being compared by the authors). Other techniques for dealing with redundancy include descriptor decomposition (for instance, via principal component analysis), but these techniques "commonly distort the original representation in ways that can render interpretation more difficult" [33], which would defeat the point of having intuitive-to-use perceptual descriptors. In our study of the AudioCommons timbral descriptors we have employed the metrics from equations 2.1, 2.2 and the Spearman correlation (ρ_S) from equation 2.3, to evaluate their redundancy or orthogonality.

Chapter 3

Methods

To find out how these perceptual descriptors behave in large databases and what their information characteristics are, we performed statistical analysis on two different audio collections. As we stated in the state of the art, in section 2.2, there has been a lack of investigation into the possibilities of using timbral descriptors directly for audio browsing purposes. Our hypothesis is that statistical analysis of these descriptors may be helpful in designing a browsing system prototype that can take full advantage of the descriptors. Analysis of timbral descriptor data consisted of computing distributions, correlations and measures of information content, first on an environmental sound dataset, then on a set of sounds from twenty-one highly popular queries on Freesound.

The results of these timbral descriptors analyses influenced some aspects of the implementation of the search results filtering prototype. This resulted in a *Prototype* similar to Freesound's actual website but with an added timbral filtering feature. We will present this further in section 3.2. The analysis and filtering system design stages were followed by an online user evaluation of the *Prototype*, which will be covered in section 3.3.

3.1 Offline Descriptor Analysis

First we will detail our proposed descriptor analysis, starting with the specificities of the computations involved in the analysis, followed by a presentation of the two datasets used and the analysis results obtained from them in sections 3.1.2 and 3.1.3.

3.1.1 Analysis Computation Details

We used the techniques presented in subsection 2.3 to compute typical statistical distributions and central tendency measurements, correlations, and information content of each of the seven timbral descriptors (those in table 1, section 2.1) in each of the two datasets. These computations consisted of: *Distributions*, *Descriptor Correlation*, and *Information Content*.

These were implemented as Python functions, using the *Pandas*¹ package for data manipulation in tables, and the *scikit-learn*² package for normalization of data and principal component analysis.

Distributions

Following Peeters et al. [10], *Median* and *Interquartile Range (IQR)* were chosen as more robust summarization statistics than *Mean* and *Standard Deviation*, to get a sense of the central tendency of timbral descriptor data, as well as its range.

Descriptor Correlation

The decision to use the Spearman Rank Correlation (ρ_s), instead of the Pearson product-moment correlation (ρ_p), for each pair of timbral descriptors is justified as follows:

1. As will be shown in sections 3.1.2 and 3.1.3, timbral descriptor data produces heavy-tailed distributions. De Winter et al. [34] compared the two measures

¹<https://pandas.pydata.org/>

²<https://scikit-learn.org/stable/>

with regards to variability, bias with respect to the population value, and presence of outliers, and found ρ_s more suitable for heavy-tailed distributions or if outliers are present.

2. Peeters et al. [10] further support the use of ρ_s over ρ_p since the former is robust to (non-linear) monotone transforms of the data. They give the following example: "the rank correlation between the fundamental frequency and the log of the fundamental frequency equals one when focusing on ranks, whereas the Pearson correlation between the same variables is lower than one"[10].

We compute the Spearman Rank Correlation as implemented in the *Scipy*³ Python package, which follows the formulation given by Zwillinger & Kokoska [35]. We have omitted the corresponding p-values for this analysis step since, for all Spearman correlations in both datasets, $p\text{-value} < 0.01$.

Information Content

The first information content measure used is the Weighted Average Loading Indicator (*WALDI*), proposed by Mitrovic et al.[31]. As stated in chapter 2, section 2.3, it is measure of information with respect to the feature's variance, and is computed following equation 2.1. This measure is based on Principal Component Analysis (PCA); the feature loadings needed to compute it (see equation 2.1) were calculated using *scikit-learn*'s implementation⁴ of PCA. The feature loadings of a given descriptor consist of those principal components that explain most of its variance, i.e. with an *Eigenvalue* ≥ 1.0 , which can be accessed by indexing *scikit-learn*'s PCA interface `PCA.components_` with the conditional `PCA.explained_variance_ ≥ 1.0` .

For contrasting the results of the WALDI measure, *entropy* is also calculated, as per equation 2.2 from section 2.3. As shown in listing 3.1.1, this measure required quantizing the original descriptor data (in the range $[0, 100]$) into 256 bins to allow

³<https://docs.scipy.org/doc/scipy/reference/generated/scipy.stats.spearmanr.html>

⁴<https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.decomposition.PCA.html>

Listing 3.1: Python code for computing Shannon entropy of a descriptor

```
def entropy(self, feature):
    '''
    Parameters:
    feature (str): descriptor to select from dataset
    Returns:
    float: entropy, H(f)
    '''
    feature_data = self.descriptor_data.loc[:, feature]
    total = feature_data.size
    # Quantize data to (0, 255)
    feature_data = feature_data.apply(lambda x: round((x*2.55)+1.0))
    # Calc prob(bin_value) from given distribution
    entropy = 0.0
    for bin_value in range(256):
        prob = float((feature_data == bin_value).sum()) / total
    if prob > 0.0:
        # Multiply prob by log2(prob), and sum over all values
        entropy += - prob * math.log2(prob)
    return entropy
```

Animals	Natural soundscapes & water sounds	Human, non-speech sounds	Interior/domestic sounds	Exterior/urban noises
Dog	Rain	Crying baby	Door knock	Helicopter
Rooster	Sea waves	Sneezing	Mouse click	Chainsaw
Pig	Crackling fire	Clapping	Keyboard typing	Siren
Cow	Crickets	Breathing	Door, wood creaks	Car horn

Figure 3: ESC50 Dataset Categories⁶

the calculation of the probability $p(i)$ of the i -th bin for any descriptor, yielding entropy in units *bit per byte*.

3.1.2 ESC50 Dataset Analysis

As previously mentioned in section 1.1, *field-recording* is amongst the most popular tags found in Freesound, according to research ([2], [5]) and Freesound's recent yearly report "2019 in numbers" ⁵. This motivated our first analysis, which was performed on the ESC50 dataset [36], a popular audio dataset for sound classification, tagging, and sound event detection tasks [37].

The ESC50 dataset [36] is comprised of 2000 environmental sound clips from 50

⁵<https://blog.freesound.org/?p=1084>

different classes (e.g. *dog*, *footsteps*, *train*, etc), which can be arranged into 5 broad categories (shown in figure 3). These five categories –*Animals*, *Natural soundscapes* & *water sounds*, *Human, non-speech sounds*, *Interior/domestic sounds*, and *Exterior/urban noises*– were used to group our analysis instead of the individual sound classes. The sounds in the dataset are 5-second-long clips that have been extracted from Freesound recordings, which is appropriate for our purposes. These clips, however, often belong to longer recordings from Freesound. Additionally, sometimes two or more consecutive clips are fragments belonging to the same source recording (i.e. different dataset audio files may share the same Freesound ID), which comparatively increases the presence of the source recording in the dataset. Since the timbral descriptors under analysis are temporal averages of frame-wise and onset-wise features, we had to consider how this editing of original recordings into 5-second clips may affect our analysis. Clips sourced from the same recording may have almost identical timbral descriptor values if the original recording is quite homogeneous, or highly different if the original recording is heterogeneous; any of these two cases would bias the analysis by either concentrating results around the median in excess (homogeneous sounds) or by spreading results and increasing IQR (heterogeneous sounds). Therefore, we decided to briefly investigate and compare the distribution of timbral descriptors in each of the following two cases:

1. *Fragmented audio data*: 5-second long clips as provided in the ESC50 dataset. This consists of a total of 2000 sounds, 400 in each category.
2. *Source recordings*: full-length Freesound recordings where clips from the ESC50 dataset were taken from. This consisted of a total of 1237 sounds (763 fewer sounds than the original dataset) due to the following practical limitation that conditioned how we could retrieve this data: while the implementation of the timbral models by Pearce et al. [38] is open-source ⁷, running them on a personal computer for sounds of several minutes took too long (some of these full-length source recordings corresponding to ESC50 clips are 12 minutes long

⁶retrieved from: <https://github.com/karolpiczak/ESC-50>

⁷https://github.com/AudioCommons/timbral_models

src_file	category	ac_depth	ac_warmth	ac_hardness	ac_roughness	ac_boominess	ac_brightness	ac_sharpness	
1	100038	natural_soundsapes_and_water_sounds	27.786454041966373	28.864170644327917	61.68802403866107	52.78059202712951	4.020670860860918	77.7654851265131	69.39346036880406
16	115521	natural_soundsapes_and_water_sounds	63.810688532683784	58.59703800658046	36.44665175702302	37.11350389871642	48.340593524773865	41.41846556861593	25.689944619910666
27	118559	natural_soundsapes_and_water_sounds	26.557700937922093	31.1287658774377	65.04441912678661	60.27477423017675	9.974289830014069	74.37632553727559	62.79391992439037
30	12653	natural_soundsapes_and_water_sounds	38.40089327315104	37.39932057919309	68.88379525159081	45.054619329010535	24.853553933199986	63.39500140544477	50.28078024232286
31	12654	natural_soundsapes_and_water_sounds	30.809779743571227	33.652630863845786	69.49393766891905	33.571045967641695	25.560973537546545	69.06427697121813	58.13506833560638
50	16746	natural_soundsapes_and_water_sounds	35.569999932646119	28.15377690450199	79.76075478552116	51.27885193990222	12.639999025232827	63.65760288635439	66.24614923496596
54	17150	natural_soundsapes_and_water_sounds	44.19238257851562	32.659382409829405	74.38623240340141	46.38355842209941	27.261925575336228	81.54078415329704	69.47643910253811
62	17367	natural_soundsapes_and_water_sounds	38.5629389367566	29.84102126638782	64.9065062716793	70.26096074652133	11.886776386129366	75.61245823160982	65.07961873323904

Table 3: Excerpt of descriptor data from ESC50 dataset files, after selection (case 2, *Source recordings*), where each row represents a sound. This figure shows the Freesound ID of the source recording, the broad category it belongs to, and timbral descriptor data on separate columns.

or more). Consequently, this is how we sourced the timbral descriptor data for this case:

- If the length of a sound was less than 30 seconds, their descriptor data was retrieved via the Freesound API ⁸, since this is faster than local computation.
- If the length of a sound was between 30 seconds and 120 seconds, an *.ogg* format preview of the sound was downloaded and their descriptor data was computed locally using the available Python implementation, given that the Freesound API does not provide this data for sounds longer than 30 seconds.
- If the length of a sound was greater than 120 seconds, the sound was discarded.

Table 3 shows a sample of the data used for this analysis. For this comparison we were only interested in looking at the distributions (and not correlation or information content), which we visualized as conventional boxplots with whiskers indicating $1.5 * IQR$, and outliers as red dots. In both cases, the analysis was performed on a per category basis, as well as on the full dataset, and for each timbral descriptor.

⁸<https://freesound.org/docs/api/index.html>

Figure 4: Distributions per category (and full dataset on lower-right corner), for case 1: *Fragmented audio data*.

Figure 5: Distributions per category (and all 1237 sounds on lower-right corner), for case 2: *Source recordings*.

As can be seen from figures 4 and 5, analogous categories between both cases show

closely placed medians (green line) and interquartile ranges (black boxes), with the overall shape of timbral descriptor distributions bearing a high degree of similarity between cases, even though the *Source recordings* consisted of fewer data points. This was promising with regards to the prototype and how many data points would be needed to provide the user with a representative distribution of sounds for their query. We will address this again in our analysis of the second dataset, consisting of popular Freesound queries, in section 3.1.3. The biggest difference is found in outliers, which seem to be slightly less spread out and more densely concentrated for the *Fragmented audio data* case (figure 4) than for case 2 (figure 5), and probably due to the greater size of the dataset in case 1.

Given the similarities in these results, we chose to proceed with the rest of the analysis using the timbral descriptor data of the full original ESC50 dataset, i.e. case 1: *Fragmented audio data*, since its greater number of sounds (2000, instead of 1237) would ensure slightly better accuracy.

Regarding between-category observations (see figure 4), it can be seen that some descriptors such as *brightness* or *hardness* tend to exhibit values in the upper half of the $[0, 100]$ range, while the *boominess* descriptor tends to stay in the lower half of that range. The latter descriptor also shows some outliers into the negative values of the scale, which is acknowledged and explained by how Pearce et al. [38] implemented the model:

"Although the model was trained on subjective data ranging from 0 to 100, the output values can be beyond these scales due to the nature of the linear regression implemented."

Lastly, we will report the correlation and information content parts of the analysis for the ESC50 dataset. These are shown in figures 6 and 7. Correlation plots show inter-descriptor Spearman Rank Correlation. Yellow and green colors represent positive correlation, while dark blue represents negative correlation. Green-blue color represents correlation values around zero, which indicates a pair of descriptors

are uncorrelated. The yellow diagonal that goes from the top-left to the bottom-right corners shows maximum positive correlation of each descriptor with itself, as expected. Overall, the following relationships can be observed between pairs of descriptors across all categories:

- Strong positive correlation: (*sharpness*, *brightness*), (*sharpness*, *hardness*), (*depth*, *warmth*), (*depth*, *boominess*), and (*warmth*, *boominess*).
- Strong negative correlation: (*brightness*, *warmth*), (*brightness*, *boominess*), (*sharpness*, *boominess*), (*sharpness*, *warmth*), (*hardness*, *warmth*)

Most of these relationships seem to make intuitive sense. Generally, timbral descriptors whose implementation focuses on a similar area of the spectrum (e.g. bass frequencies for *boominess*, *depth*, or *warmth*) show positive correlation amongst them, while showing negative correlation with those descriptors whose implementation focuses on a different area of the spectrum (e.g. on mid-high frequencies or onsets for *brightness*, *sharpness*, or *hardness*). However, such similarity between correlation matrices of different categories of sounds could be due to the inherent sonic variety within such broad categories. Collections of sounds for different search queries may be less heterogeneous, so we will present how correlations amongst descriptors behave in that case in the next section. Even if these similarities are not consistent amongst queries, correlation information from a single query may prove useful for only presenting to the user a selection of the descriptors, discarding one of every highly correlated pair.

The information content measures presented on figure 7 are meant to be complementary to the correlation information. However, no considerable differences can be seen amongst descriptors for either measure, WALDI or entropy. The two measures also provide conflicting information. Whilst according to the WALDI measure (in red on figure 7) *roughness* is the least informative descriptor across all categories of the ESC50 dataset, it is as informative as others.

Next section looks at the same analysis procedure on the second dataset, which provided data closer to a real search scenario on Freesound.

Figure 6: Spearman Correlation between descriptors per category (and full ESC50 dataset on lower-right corner).

Figure 7: WALDI and entropy measures per descriptor, per category (and full ESC50 dataset on lower-right corner).

3.1.3 Popular Queries Analysis

whoosh	piano	birds	fire	bass	trap	808
music	intro	wind	car	beat	vocal	rain
click	guitar	pop	bell	woosh	swoosh	explosion

Table 4: Selected top Freesound queries for analysis

The dataset of popular Freesound queries was assembled from real user queries to Freesound during the month-long term from March 22nd 2020 until April 20th 2020. The total amount of queries in said period was filtered to obtain only unique ones, which reduced the original set to 1127479, and the 50 most occurring queries from the period were kept. An unexpected query ("brampton", a city in Canada), coming from automated requests by a bot, was found amongst this top 50. The latter query was removed and, to remove any other unusual queries from the original month-long period (e.g. due to temporal events, or bot requests), their intersection with the top 15 queries of the day prior to computation was taken. The final selection consisted of the union of said intersection with the top 10 queries from the month-long period to ensure those were still kept in the final set. Equation 3.1 formally shows this process, where $Queries$ is a function that returns the set of user queries for a given date or range, and top_N in a function that finds the N most frequent items in a given set.

$$\begin{aligned}
 month &= Queries([22 - 03 - 2020, 20 - 04 - 2020]) \\
 day &= Queries(11 - 06 - 2020) \\
 selection &= (top_{50}(month) \cap top_{15}(day)) \cup top_{10}(month)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3.1}$$

This selection process produced a total of 21 queries, shown in table 4. Then, Freesound's API Python client ⁹ was used to assemble the descriptor data needed for analysis. Text-based search was performed for each of the selected 21 queries. To ensure Freesound's API could provide the necessary pre-computed data, since that

⁹<https://github.com/MTG/freesound-python>

would be the data used by the prototype, timbral descriptor data was requested only for results with *duration* < 30seconds. This resulted in dataset sizes of between 180 and 4353 sounds, as shown in table 5.

Query	Number of sounds	Query	Number of sounds	Query	Number of sounds
trap	180	explosion	1046	guitar	1985
808	221	piano	1143	car	2036
swoosh	434	pop	1239	vocal	2267
woosh	519	fire	1333	click	2367
whoosh	543	birds	1443	music	3352
intro	698	wind	1747	beat	3701
rain	851	bell	1781	bass	4353

Table 5: Number of sound results per selected query (i.e. size of each sub-set of the second dataset).

There was one addition to our analysis procedure for this dataset, motivated by a prototype design consideration. In order to avoid making server requests for unnecessarily large amounts of data, but still show users descriptor distributions that are representative of their query results (see figure 14), we had to investigate how timbral descriptor distributions for real search queries varied according to the amount of (audio) search results that were taken into account. To that end, we inserted the logic shown in algorithm 1 into the distributions computation stage (comprising median, IQR, and outliers).

Algorithm 1 Pseudocode for IQR-stabilization checking program, for a single query. Here *memory* sets how many iterations the circular buffer can "remember" IRQ data for.

```

for descriptor in timbral_descriptors do
  initialize circular_buffer(descriptor, memory = 5)
end for
total_data_size ← query_descriptor_data.size
for i = 15 to total_data_size with step = 15 do
  data_chunk ← query_descriptor_data[: i]
  for descriptor in timbral_descriptors do
    append IQR(data_chunk[descriptor]) to circular_buffer[descriptor].data
  end for
  {Check circular_buffer memory for each descriptor}
  if ( $-1.0 < IQR\_differences > 1.0$ ) during last circular_buffer.memory iterations then
    write i to log file
    {at i number of sounds, IQR is not changing considerably anymore}
  end if
end for

```

The results of the stabilization-checking procedure presented in algorithm 1 are shown in table 6. The query *guitar* needed the greatest amount of sounds to stabilize

Query	Logged message
bass	<i>IQR has stabilized. 195 data points were needed.</i>
beat	<i>IQR has stabilized. 180 data points were needed.</i>
bell	<i>IQR has stabilized. 285 data points were needed.</i>
birds	<i>IQR has stabilized. 300 data points were needed.</i>
car	<i>IQR has stabilized. 240 data points were needed.</i>
click	<i>IQR has stabilized. 255 data points were needed.</i>
explosion	<i>IQR has stabilized. 270 data points were needed.</i>
fire	<i>IQR has stabilized. 225 data points were needed.</i>
guitar	<i>IQR has stabilized. 390 data points were needed.</i>
intro	<i>IQR has stabilized. 345 data points were needed.</i>
music	<i>IQR has stabilized. 360 data points were needed.</i>
piano	<i>IQR has stabilized. 285 data points were needed.</i>
pop	<i>IQR has stabilized. 225 data points were needed.</i>
rain	<i>IQR has stabilized. 240 data points were needed.</i>
swoosh	<i>IQR has stabilized. 255 data points were needed.</i>
trap	<i>(180 sounds retrieved, stabilization was not reached)</i>
vocal	<i>IQR has stabilized. 225 data points were needed.</i>
whoosh	<i>IQR has stabilized. 330 data points were needed.</i>
wind	<i>IQR has stabilized. 195 data points were needed.</i>
woosh	<i>IQR has stabilized. 360 data points were needed.</i>
808	<i>(221 sounds retrieved, stabilization was not reached)</i>

Table 6: Query and corresponding number of sounds needed for the IQR to stabilize, as per algorithm 1.

(390), while the queries *bass* and *woosh* required the least (195). The median number of sounds (across queries) required for the IQR to stabilize is 255. The other analysis computations performed on this dataset are the same as those performed on the ESC50 dataset in the previous section. The data from the distribution analysis is shown in figures 8 to 13. Distribution data for all twenty-one queries analyzed (i.e. median, first quartile, and third quartile) are plotted together to show the overall distribution patterns followed, which are shared by most queries, as can be appreciated. The plots for each of the three statistics are shown in pairs (per page, figures 8 and 9; figures 10 and 11; and figures 12 and 13), where the first figure in the pair shows the statistic results when taking all available sounds for each query, and the second figure in the pair shows the statistic results when taking an amount of sounds only up to the cutoff determined during the IQR stabilization calculation (algorithm 1) for each query. Note these two calculation are based on

exactly the same amount of sounds for queries *808* and *trap*, since they did not reach stabilization of their IQR (as stated in table 6). The overall similarity between pairs of plots for each statistic, with few exceptions, justifies one of the effects of the analysis presented here on the design of the prototype, explained later in section 3.2.2. Within-query comparisons in plots accounting for all retrieved sounds (figures 8, 10 and 12) reveal an interesting behaviour: each timbral descriptors under study appears to concentrate on a specific region for most queries, which seems quite marked even considering a relatively limited number of queries.

Further study is needed to find out if this trend continues with a larger number of queries, popular and more rare. This behaviour suggests that the implementation of these descriptors could be adjusted or their scales warped in such a way that they can provide better separation between different sounds or sound groups. There are mainly two queries that stand apart from others: *bass* and *808* (a popular type of electronic kick drum sound [39]). These queries have much higher medians and first quartile (Q1) values for the *depth* descriptor, which is expected since this descriptor's implementation¹⁰ is tightly dependent on content in the lower-end of the spectrum. This difference is less marked for the third quartile statistic, which represents the upper bound of the distribution's spread, and again shows (if *bass* and *808* are some of the "bassiest" sounds in the dataset) how further study is required into the scaling of these descriptors.

Due to space limitations and to ease consultation, we have collected the plots resulting from correlation analysis in the Appendix of this thesis (see section A.1). These show the Spearman Rank correlation matrices for all twenty-one queries analysed. Overall, the same positive/negative correlation patterns can be observed as for the ESC50 dataset (see figure 6). We observe two main differences with respect to the ESC50 dataset:

- Descriptor correlations seem more extreme for queries *808*, *rain*, *whoosh/woosh/swoosh*, and *wind* (figures 41, 34, 38/40/35, and 39 respectively), particularly the neg-

¹⁰https://github.com/AudioCommons/timbral_models/blob/master/timbral_models/Timbral_Depth.py

Figure 8: Popular queries median statistic for each timbral descriptor. Based on all sounds retrieved for each query. A general line pattern can be observed.

Figure 9: Popular queries median statistic for each timbral descriptor. Based only on the amount of sounds up to the cutoff determined after IQR stabilization (see table 6). A general line pattern can be observed.

Figure 10: Popular queries first percentile statistic for each timbral descriptor (Q1, lower IQR bound). Based on all sounds retrieved for each query. A general line pattern can be observed.

Figure 11: Popular queries first percentile statistic for each timbral descriptor (Q1, lower IQR bound). Based only on the amount of sounds up to the cutoff determined after IQR stabilization (see table 6). A general line pattern can be observed.

Figure 12: Popular queries third percentile statistic for each timbral descriptor (Q3, upper IQR bound). Based on all sounds retrieved for each query. A general line pattern can be observed.

Figure 13: Popular queries third percentile statistic for each timbral descriptor (Q3, upper IQR bound). Based only on the amount of sounds up to the cutoff determined after IQR stabilization (see table 6). A general line pattern can be observed.

actively correlated pairs of descriptors, shown in very dark blue. This could be due to the fact that these queries represent narrower sound groups than those of the ESC50 dataset, and the collections are less heterogeneous in this case.

- The queries *piano* and *bell* show a more marked uncorrelation between the descriptor *roughness* and the remaining 6 descriptors, which can be seen as a symmetric green-blue cross pattern on the correlation matrices (figures 32 and 23, respectively). Perhaps due to these sound groups containing more clearly tonal material, this could mean *roughness* is one of the most useful descriptors for browsing for these two queries.

3.2 Prototype Design

An online sound search prototype was built during and after offline descriptor analysis. The prototype was designed to resemble Freesound's appearance, since it is aimed at Freesound users, and will be using Freesound's content and descriptor data. However most of Freesound's features were removed (such as faceted search, forums, blog, and user login), and only the text-based search box on the top right corner was left on the interface. On the right-side bar, where Freesound would show its faceted search options, we placed the proposed timbral-descriptor-based filtering interface, based on range sliders with a bar plot display over them showing the distribution of sound results for each descriptor's range of values (see figure 14).

The prototype was built as a Python Flask¹¹ application to serve static HTML, Javascript, CSS, and image content, using the Jinja templating engine to extend and link HTML layouts for different pages. This Flask application uses the Freesound API Python client¹² previously mentioned to perform text-based and descriptor-based audio search, and provide the actual audio content to the user using embeddable `<iframe></iframe>` HTML elements. These embedded sound results can be listened to directly on the prototype site, and they all link to their original page on Freesound.org, and contain appropriate tags, so the user can interact nor-

¹¹<https://flask.palletsprojects.com/en/1.1.x/>

¹²<https://github.com/MTG/freesound-python>

Figure 14: General view of the proposed online prototype

mally with the results list. Results are limited to a duration of under 30 seconds, to allow the retrieval of corresponding timbral descriptor data, also via the API. The Flask application also makes use of the *Pandas* and *Numpy* Python packages for table manipulation of descriptor values, to get the descriptor distribution data, and to build the inverted index needed for dynamic updating of the slider distributions (see section 3.2.1). This data corresponding to a given query is then passed to an HTML template as JSON, and used to populate the distribution barplots over the sliders.

The timbral descriptor filtering panel on the right of the website is built using the Javascript libraries *noUiSlider* and *Chart.js* to render the range sliders and bar plots, respectively. All seven timbral descriptors (see table 1) were included in the slider-based interface. These can be dragged to select a specific range of descriptor values (e.g. only very high *brightness* values), and once the user has adjusted the filters as they wanted they can press a "Filter Search Results" button at the bottom of the side panel, which will submit a new GET request for their initial query but with the additional timbral filters. This approach using a "Filter Search Results" button was chosen over an instant page update (e.g. upon releasing the mouse on any slider) on the basis that if a user wants to adjust all seven filters, it may be

Figure 15: Two filters prior to adjustment. *Roughness* has full range selected.

Figure 16: Same filters, post-adjustment. *Roughness*'s range has been narrowed down. The distribution shown over the *Hardness* filter has changed correspondingly.

annoying to wait the page to update seven times. The instant update procedure would only incur a time-cost because the prototype has to query Freesound's API; this would not be the case if our proposed filtering feature was integrated into the actual Freesound site, which has much faster access to the content in its databases.

3.2.1 Dynamic distribution updates

To make the filters responsive and prevent users from reaching an empty results page, the distribution barplots were designed to constantly update as any slider is adjusted by a user. Figures 15 and 16 show an example of this in action, for the query "glitch". Adjusting a slider modifies distributions over the other filters, since it implies constraining the amount of search results that satisfy the selected descriptor value range. This was implemented using what Tzanetakis refers to as *Usage-based indexing* [17], whereby data (in our case descriptor data) is indexed according to what the user interface supports, as opposed to allowing arbitrary search. In Tzanetakis' own words:

"Each filter is represented as a list of lists of files. The lists are doubly

linked. The first level corresponds to the possible settings for each filter and the lists of files correspond to the files that satisfy a particular filter setting. For categorical items the first level list has a list of files for each category. For continuous attributes quantization bins are used for the first level. [...] The list corresponding to the current setting is called the active list. Therefore for each attribute there is an active list, and the files that satisfy all the attributes, can be found by finding their intersection (all the files that are common to all active lists)."

Figure 17 shows Tzanetakis' process for finding the list of files that satisfy the criteria given by two attribute selections (i.e. slider adjustments in our system).

Figure 17: Intersection process for usage-based indexing, retrieved from [17].

For our proposed filtering system, this means quantizing the timbral descriptors in the range $[0, 100]$ to one hundred integer values only (i.e. no decimal values). For each timbral descriptor, an inverted index [4] is constructed (in the Flask server, upon receiving a response from the Freesound API), consisting of every possible quantized descriptor value as keys, and lists of associated Freesound IDs for the returned results that have a given quantized descriptor value. Table 7 shows an example of this. These indices are implemented as simple Javascript objects, where each entry consists of a possible quantized descriptor value (a possible "filter setting", according to Tzanetakis' wording), and an array of Freesound IDs (the "files that satisfy a particular filter setting", according to Tzanetakis).

<i>Warmth</i>	Freesound IDs
0	457832, 34982, 112220
1	73954, 67232
2	–
3	88659
...	...
98	832221, 90993, 23153, 12988, 84322
99	77463, 233341
100	–

Table 7: Example of the inverted descriptor index structure as would be generated by the Flask server and sent as JSON to the front-end. It shows quantized descriptor values on the left column, and corresponding sound IDs on the right.

Since our proposed prototype allows the selection of *ranges*, not individual values, the intersection procedure shown in figure 17 is slightly different. Whenever a filter slider (F) is adjusted, the following happens in the front-end:

1. Get current range selection $[a, b]$ from F.
2. Get references to sliders other than F.
3. Get the distribution of slider F, and retrieve Freesound IDs associated to range $[a, b]$: ids_{ab} .
4. Initialize *updated_distribution* array, for each of the sliders other than F.
5. For every other slider, and quantized descriptor value (0, 100): filter the other sliders' Freesound ID lists with ids_{ab} (if these are present in the former), and append the length of the new lists to its *updated_distribution* array.
6. Trigger graphic update of barplots with the *updated_distributions* data.

This allows showing the user how their filter selection has affected the distribution of results on the other filters, ensuring that there is always something to retrieve, or allowing the retrieval of outlier sounds.

3.2.2 Effects of Offline Descriptor Analysis on Prototype Design

Least Results for Reliable Distributions Representation

Earlier in section 3.1.3 we presented our analysis of timbral descriptors from popular Freesound queries and, specifically, the stabilization of their IQR as the size of the sounds considered grows. For the queries analysed, and under our stabilization-checking procedure explained in algorithm 1, we found that the amount of sounds necessary until IQR stabilized ranged from 150 to 350 approximately. We consider our notion of "stable" to have been strict: at any point, IQR differences between the past 5 iterations of adding descriptor data in steps of 15 had to be within $(-0.999, 0.999)$ for all seven timbral descriptors to yield "stable" and stop the analysis. Together with Freesound's API limit of 150 sounds per individual request, this substantiates our decision to make a single query for 150 sounds to built the distributions from. In terms of response speed, and therefore user experience, making a single 150-sounds request instead of multiple 150-sounds request (when basing our distributions on several hundred data points) proved to be roughly more than twice faster: from 9-10 second response, to about 4 second response.

Automatic Selection of Filter Subset

Following from our analysis of the correlations between timbral descriptors, it may be a possibility for the prototype to determine, on query-time, which timbral descriptors may be redundant for a given query. Streich and Ong briefly mention the difficulty of staying aware of four dimensions in their browsing system [19], so perhaps showing fewer than the total of seven descriptors we may avoid excessive cognitive load on the user. Most importantly for usability, some combinations of multiple timbral filters at once could have a hard-to-perceive effect on the search results.

We however decided not to implement this for the first version of the prototype. Since the semantic relationship between timbral descriptor and query is relevant, we could not simply choose descriptors based on which are the least correlated and

encode the greatest amount of information. For example, providing the *boominess* descriptor (together with, say, *brightness*) for a "rain" query may not make sense semantically for the user, even if they were the most uncorrelated for the given query, and highly informative compared to the other descriptors. Consequently, we will leave this as an avenue for further work. We believe gathering user feedback about this question in particular may help establish patterns for how query-dependent descriptor filter selection could be performed.

3.3 User Evaluation Methods

Evaluation in Music Information Retrieval has long focused on using the system's outputs as proxy to evaluate users' satisfaction. Urbano et al. [40] argue that "including real users in experiments is expensive and complex, and there are ethical issues to consider" and add other concerns such as lack of reproducibility. As such, traditionally MIR evaluations actually characterise the system response rather than users' responses [40]. This is possible when the system being evaluated has been designed to perform a specific task, usually modelling some aspect of the music data being analysed, or performing quick lookup of a specific data point of interest. In the context of user-contributed audio databases such as Freesound, the browsing task that the system allows is always retrieval of audio files, but it can be somewhat open-ended. And, although a user may seek a specific sound, it is not exactly equivalent to information lookup [4]. When used in artistic and multimedia production contexts, users may want to explore the database to see what is available. In such exploratory tasks, serendipity, i.e. showing the user sounds they were not looking for but still like, may be a positive aspect in the design of the browsing system [7].

Tzanetakis [17] evaluates his audio browsing system by means of a target-matching experiment, instructing users to find a given sound file within a collection of 200 by using his proposed new interface versus a conventional directory-based one. First, this would not be representative of regular Freesound usage, where a user may know what kind of sound they want (e.g. a "rain" sound, or a "drum loop") but will rarely have a specific file in mind, since they won't know most of the contents of Freesound's

collection. Secondly, if a user was coming back to Freesound for a specific sound they had previously encountered and liked, text-based querying, search history, and other faceted search features in the site would likely be enough for successful retrieval. The filters proposed in this thesis, which aim to broaden sound discovery, specifically by browsing through timbre characteristics, cannot be measured via a conventional retrieval task.

3.3.1 Survey Design

Therefore, we decided to perform evaluation of the online prototype using a survey. This survey was available directly on the prototype site in a drop-down tab, as seen in figure 18. It was based predominantly on Likert scale questions [41], and open-ended text feedback. We were interested in retrieving the following information from users:

- Users' ability to perceive a clear effect of the proposed timbre-based results-filtering through playback of their search result sounds.
- The clarity of the proposed interface to perform such filtering, i.e. it is not confusing or overwhelming for the user.
- Which of the descriptors, if any, were most useful to users of the prototype.

Figure 18 shows the Likert scale section of the survey. We asked for some contextual information related to how the users were using the prototype: *i)* looking for a specific sound, *ii)* browsing the search results for a sound they liked, or *iii)* exploring what is available in Freesound. The first Likert scale was aimed at finding out how clear the function of the filtering sliders was to users. The second refers to the how perceivable the timbral filters are on the search results. The third and last Likert scale refers to how understandable the distribution barplots over the sliders were to users, as well as their usefulness in adjusting the filters (i.e. UI-related). The second section of the survey, shown in figure 19, shows a drag-and-drop question meant to collect data about the most useful timbral descriptors for users. The last

survey section consists of text fields for the user to enter more general feedback about usability and overall design impressions (figure 20).

Tell us what you thought!

User Evaluation Form

Please, complete the following form to the best of your abilities. It should only take 5 minutes or less.

Context

Which option best describes what you're doing?

- ✓ --Please choose an option--
- Looking for a specific sound
- Browsing the search results for a sound I like
- Exploring what's available in Freesound

The meaning of the filters was clear enough.

Strongly disagree Disagree Neither Agree Nor Disagree Agree Strongly agree

Adjusting the filters had a clear and predictable impact on the search results.

Strongly disagree Disagree Neither Agree Nor Disagree Agree Strongly agree

The meaning of the barplots over each filter was clear and helped adjusting them.

Strongly disagree Disagree Neither Agree Nor Disagree Agree Strongly agree

Figure 18: First part of the prototype evaluation survey: Likert scale.

In order to get some real users of Freesound to test the prototype, a link to the prototype (with the survey) was posted to Freesound's forum pages¹³ with a brief description of the prototype and three simple steps to follow:

1. Search for something
2. Try the sliders on the right side of the page
3. Click on "Tell us what you thought!" when you are done and complete a short survey.

¹³<https://freesound.org/forum/>

Filter Relevance to Query

Pick the 3 filters that were most relevant/useful for you particular use case and query (drag & drop, order does not matter):

boominess

roughness

sharpness

warmth

depth

hardness

brightness

Which query where these filters useful for? (i.e. what you typed into the search bar)

Figure 19: Second part of the prototype evaluation survey: descriptor selection. Note users are also asked to enter the query for which the selected descriptors were useful.

Overall Impression:

Describe the things you liked about the proposed filtering system:

Describe the things you did NOT like about the proposed filtering system:

Please type here any other comments you might have...

Figure 20: Last part of the prototype evaluation survey: open-ended textual feedback.

Over the course of a month we managed to collect seven user responses to the survey. In the next chapter we will show the results collected from this survey and analyse the user responses, as well as trace connections between the descriptor analysis of sections 3.1.2 and 3.1.3, and users' responses and experience with the prototype.

Chapter 4

Results

4.1 Prototype Evaluation: User responses

Given the limited number of survey responses received, we will outline the results focusing on what proportion ($x/7$) of the total number of users gave a specific response. We refer the reader to appendix A.2, which contains the raw results of the user survey as retrieved from the database, in case it is of interest. The results presented here may not be representative given the sample size ($n=7$), but they may nonetheless provide insight valuable for future research, useful feedback regarding user interface design, and the potential for using descriptors like AudioCommons' timbral descriptors in browsing scenarios.

Firstly, regarding use context, most users indicated they were using the prototype to explore what is available in Freesound's collection ($5/7$ users). In terms of how understandable the functioning of the filters was (Likert question 1), $5/7$ users either agreed or strongly agreed that their meaning was clear. In Likert question 2, $4/7$ users agreed or strongly agreed that the filters had a clear effect on the search results; $2/7$ were neutral and one disagreed. With regards to the meaning of the distribution barplots shown over the sliders (Likert question 3), user responses were mixed and toward extremes, with $3/7$ users strongly agreeing that the barplots were meaningful and/or useful, while $4/7$ users disagreed.

Descriptor	Times selected by users
warmth	4
brightness	4
depth	2
roughness	5
sharpness	4
hardness	1
boominess	1

Table 8: Aggregate number of times each timbral descriptor was selected as useful for some query by users in the survey.

Table 8 shows how many times each descriptor was selected by the users (in aggregate) as useful for some query. The most frequently selected descriptor was *roughness*, followed by *warmth*, *brightness*, and *sharpness*. As can be seen in table 10, in appendix A.2, the queries submitted by the users were all different and many were quite uncommon (e.g. "masking tape" or "roomtone") and/or multiple queries where a single one was expected (e.g. "ping, growl, bacon").

Whilst the open-ended comments from part 3 of the survey were quite mixed and varied, two recurrent topics can be found. First, 4/7 users made comments about the search results not updating automatically as they changed any slider. Second, 3/7 users commented that they did not understand why all sliders changed whenever they adjusted one, while only one of them commented on the same matter positively ("Good cross-filter responsiveness").

4.2 Discussion

Overall, the feedback is quite mixed. Specifically, users add issues with the layout of the prototype (one user did not specify more), but others found the "Filter Search Results" button that applies the filters uncomfortable, since it was at the bottom of the page, and they had to click it constantly to apply the filters as they tried them. They also comment on the fact that the filters take up a lot of space on the page. The two most predominant aspects that can be extracted from the survey data relate to user interface and value of the timbral descriptor for audio browsing.

First, user responses to the third Likert scale question, about the meaningfulness or usefulness of the displayed barplots, were mostly negative (3 strongly agree vs 4 disagree). We attribute this to the lack of information around the axes of the barplots. One way to mitigate this would be adding a small pop-up text upon hovering over the barplots that lets the user know that those bars represent available results for a given filter value.

Next, the selection of the most useful sliders was also quite divided. They mostly match our expectations regarding the descriptor analysis performed in sections 3.1.2 and 3.1.3. As is apparent from the correlation matrices produced during the analysis of either dataset, *roughness* is the most uncorrelated descriptor with the rest, especially for queries "bell" and "piano", which happened to be one of the queries attempted by a user; this user however did not select *roughness* for this part of the survey. The users that did choose this descriptor as useful, however, searched for sounds such as "growl", "masking tape", "Ocean", or "human voice", which are sounds that can often be more noisy or textural. Thus, it may be correct to assume, as we did in section 3.2.2 deciding not to implement an automatic filter selection feature based purely on correlation data from a given query. This shows there could be a strong semantic component to browsing using timbral descriptors, even when descriptors may not be the most uncorrelated, but further research should be carried out on this topic. The second most chosen descriptors were *brightness* and *warmth* which, according to correlation analyses, tend to be strongly negatively correlated. *Sharpness*, however, was chosen equally as often as the former two, even though it tends to be highly correlated with brightness, which lends more weight to our argument that semantics probably play a big role in the use of timbral descriptors for audio browsing. *Depth* and *boominess* were only chosen 2 and 1 time, respectively, which is reasonable given the queries submitted: none of the sounds searched tends to have much audio content in the bass frequencies.

Other feedback given by users was a suggestion to change *roughness* for "clarity", which could be understood as an opposite concept, perhaps how this user perceived its effect on the search results. Another user suggests having undo/redo options to

be able to move between the history of filter adjustments, and, in a similar vein, another user comments on how selecting a filter range removes the outside of said range from the distribution, forcing the user to start again if they want that part of the distribution available.

Chapter 5

Conclusion

In this thesis we have found recurring patterns in distributions of timbral audio descriptors modelled on human perception. These patterns seem to be somewhat inherent to the descriptors as demonstrated in our analyses of two audio datasets. Some of the behaviours observed on descriptors can be applicable to the design of audio browsing interfaces, as stated in section 3.2.2. The proposed browsing prototype provides insight into users' preferences and can serve as a guide for future research on audio browsing based on timbral audio descriptors, but is probably not representative of a broader set of users.

5.1 Further Work

Apart from the small adjustments suggested by user feedback, and attempting to get more users to try the prototype, the first extension we can suggest for this work is to attempt to replicate Grill and Flexer's results with their proposed browsing visualisation but using the AudioCommons timbral descriptors as the underlying audio descriptors instead of the textural descriptors they use. We would like to compare that with our slider-based approach.

According to Andersen and Knee [7], musicians seek "surprise, opposition, individuality, and control over the recommendation process" more than "more of the same"

recommendations. Whilst they observe that the very concept of opposition itself is complex to define, a possible research path could take the timbral descriptors explored here for browsing and attempt to use them as dimensions along which to measure dissimilarity, with the benefit of providing intuitive axes of control for the user.

The AudioCommons descriptors could also be tested as potentially useful sound effects. The work by McDermott and Simoncelli [13] provides a starting point. Take *brightness* as an example: one could compute its value from a sound, specify a new desired value for *brightness*, and have a trained statistical model iteratively modify the original sound until its computed *brightness* value approached the new specified one. Of course, the feasibility of such iterative processing within a reasonable time-frame and its perceptual effect on the resulting sound would have to be tested to determine its viability as an end product for users, for example in the context of an online editor in Freesound.

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Appendix A

Appendix

A.1 Popular Queries Correlation Analysis

Correlation matrices for all twenty-one queries analysed, as presented on section 3.1.3. To avoid overloading the main chapters with excessive figure material, they are collected here to be referenced while reading. Their calculation is specified in section 3.1.1, in chapter 3.

Figure 21: Spearman Rank correlation for *bass* sounds.

Figure 22: Spearman Rank correlation for *beat* sounds.

Figure 28: Spearman Rank correlation for *fire* sounds.

Figure 29: Spearman Rank correlation for *guitar* sounds.

Figure 30: Spearman Rank correlation for *intro* sounds.

Figure 31: Spearman Rank correlation for *music* sounds.

Figure 32: Spearman Rank correlation for *piano* sounds.

Figure 33: Spearman Rank correlation for *pop* sounds.

Figure 34: Spearman Rank correlation for *rain* sounds.

Figure 40: Spearman Rank correlation for *woosh* sounds.

Figure 41: Spearman Rank correlation for 808 sounds.

A.2 Raw Survey Results

date	context	filt_meaning	filt_impact	barplot_useful
2020-08-06 14:48:26.814947	target-find	neutral	neutral	neutral
2020-08-14 19:49:58.437248	target-find	strongly_agree	strongly_agree	strongly_agree
2020-08-19 15:21:09.228600	exploring-freesound	neutral	agree	strongly_agree
2020-08-19 17:01:19.416444	exploring-freesound	agree	neutral	disagree
2020-08-19 17:23:07.840285	exploring-freesound	agree	neutral	strongly_agree
2020-08-19 17:38:22.941521	browse-for-like	strongly_agree	agree	disagree
2020-08-22 11:30:06.428911	exploring-freesound	disagree	disagree	disagree
2020-08-25 17:15:43.359927	exploring-freesound	agree	agree	disagree

Table 9: Raw survey responses for part 1 (context and Likert scale questions), as retrieved from database.

relevant_filter_1	relevant_filter_2	relevant_filter_3	relevance_which_query
descriptor-depth	descriptor-warmth	descriptor-roughness	Ocean
descriptor-brightness	descriptor-sharpness	descriptor-roughness	ping, growl, bacon
descriptor-brightness	descriptor-warmth	descriptor-roughness	jazz
descriptor-roughness	descriptor-sharpness	descriptor-boominess	masking tape
descriptor-depth	descriptor-warmth	descriptor-brightness	piano
descriptor-sharpness	descriptor-warmth	descriptor-roughness	human voice
descriptor-brightness	descriptor-hardness	descriptor-sharpness	roomtone

Table 10: Raw survey responses for part 2 (descriptor drag-and-drop selection), as retrieved from database.

liked	disliked	comments
Good cross-filter responsiveness	The filtering should be automatic (a button click action is needed) to meet the actual technologies expectations	Very useful sounds. Thank you!
I really like how the barplots change shape. This also sometimes helps explain the scale of the filters, eg which side meant "warmer", "more boomy" etc. The sliders were very easy to use.	The biggest thing I didn't like was the layout. The "filter search results" box is right at the bottom. I initially expected the results displayed to change automatically as I moved the sliders, as didn't initially see that I had to click. You also can't see all the filters on screen at the same time (but maybe that's because I have a small laptop screen). It wasn't always easy to see what which end of the scale was "more boomy", "less boomy" etc.	I like the fact that the waveforms come up when results are displayed.
It's a very interesting way to filter to find sounds based on sound characteristics.	I don't understand why when I change a slider selector for a filter, the plots of the other ones change. What is the interaction between them?	At first sight the UI is not clear. As when you modify a slider selector the effect on it's plot and the plots of other filters change in real time, it seems like it should also affect the list of sounds. The button "Filter Search Result" at the end is not very clear.
knowing how many results are available in each range of the filter values	having to apply the filter settings each time instead of the results refreshing as I applied the filters	
It's very useful to find sounds that really fit what you want sonically.	In the filters, if you select in a filter lets say from 70 to 90, the next round you can't see in the plot if there are any sound outside that range. If you want to change your mind you have to start from 0.	
narrow down the results	sometime will show irrelevant result	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. maybe roughness can change to 'clarity' 2. would be nice to have a reset button or undo/redo function so that you can still have all setup you've made 3. not too sure the function of the length of each bar on the barplots 4. when change one parameter, barplots of the other parameters also change accordingly, it's quite confusing especially when you don't fully know what's the function of the vertical axis on the plot
Please continue to improve	Please continue to improve	Please continue to improve

Table 11: Raw survey responses for part 3 (open-ended feedback), as retrieved from database.